

'A closer look at Africa's unique Afrocentric approach to Human Rights.'

Written by : Mercy Jaravani

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1. Introduction

There exists an unsettled debate on Africa's approach to Human rights. Several scholars accuse Africa of readily adopting a Western-biased human rights norms due to the political pressure and the aching need to be accepted as civilised. Scholars in support of this thought argue that African leaders had little power to influence and shape the human rights in the African context. In support, other scholars argue that when African leaders established the African human rights system, they were pre-occupied with consolidating power and little care for the protection of individual rights. Respectfully, both arguments could not be any further from the truth. A careful study of Africa's human rights system will prove that contrary to the assertions by such scholars, African States have demonstrated unique Afrocentric approach to Human rights. It can be argued that this approach has been mainly shaped by historical experiences, cultural and traditional values.

This main aim of this paper is to add voice to this debate by critically examining Africa's human rights system and providing evidence on how despite the pressure to adopt a largely Western-influenced human rights system, African leaders utilized African values, tradition and realities to conceptualize an African Human Rights System to respond to the conditions of Africa. An attempt will also be made to draw a comparison with the United Nations system and the approaches of other regions such as the Europe and the Americas. In this discussion, focus will primary zone in on the major African Treaties such as the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (known as the Banjul Charter, Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (known as the Maputo Protocol) and the Charter on the Rights of a Child.

2. Background of Human Rights

Following the collapse of the League of Nations and aftermath the World War 2, States faced mounting pressure and the urgency to establish more effective mechanisms to promote international peace and security, equality of nations and to ensure the dignity and equality of all persons. Consequently, this led to the formation of the United Nations, through the United Nations Charter in 1945. This would be followed by the adoption of the **Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)** in 1948, through the **General Assembly Resolution 217 A**. The UDHR, although not a Treaty nor a legally binding instrument, is generally accepted as the

universal standard for the basic rights and freedoms that apply to all people.¹ It has become a foundation instrument that has inspired many legally binding international human rights laws. Human rights may be understood as a set of **inalienable, indivisible, indivisible and inherent** norms and freedoms that all human beings are entitled by virtue of them being humans regardless of their background.²

The UDHR immediately gave birth to two legally-binding treaties namely, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) which would constitute the primary benchmarks or standards for international human rights law.³ Both the ICCPR and the ICESCR were adopted in 1966 under Resolution 2200A, but would later enter into force 10 years later, in 1976. The ICCPR provides for civil and political rights known as the first generation of rights, placing an obligation on States to promote and protect the political and civil rights of persons. The ICESCR on the other hand, regarded as the second generation of rights, guarantees the protection and respect of economic, social and cultural rights.

Since 1966, the framework for international human rights law has expanded, and to date there currently are at least 10 International Human Rights Treaties adopted by the United Nations, shaping today's international human rights architecture. As such, at regional level, regions such as the Europe, America and Africa have established their own human rights systems inspired by this architecture.

3. The African Charter on the Human and Peoples Rights in Africa (Banjul Charter) vis-à-vis the UDHR, ICCPR and the ICESCR

Within the African region, in efforts to establish an African Human Rights system, African States through the African Union in 1981, adopted the African Charter on the Human and Peoples' Rights in Africa. The Charter is the primary instrument for the promotion and protection of human rights in Africa. It has been correctly opined that the adoption of the Banjul Charter marked a pivotal revolution from a Eurocentric conceptualization to a more Afrocentric approach to Human Rights⁴.

The starting point would be to note that the African Approach is clearly manifest in the Preamble which places strong emphasis on the obligation of State parties to ensure that the virtues of their '*historical tradition and the values of African civilization inspire and characterize their reflection on the concept of human and peoples*'. A further reading of the Charter reflects more on the Afrocentric approach as evidenced by the following:

¹ H Hurst. "The UDHR in National and International Law." *Health and Human Rights*, Vol. 3, no. 2, 1998, pp. 144–58. *JSTOR*, <https://doi.org/10.2307/4065305>. Accessed 15 Nov. 2024.

² A Gutterman-*What are Human Rights?* 2023 p SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4320947> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4320947>

³ S.P Marks: - *Human Rights: A brief introduction*. Harvard University (2016) p2 <https://www.hsph.harvard.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/134/2016/07/Human-Rights-A-brief-intro-2016.pdf>

⁴ M Mutua "The Banjul Charter and the African cultural footprint": An evaluation of the languages of duties 1993, *Virginia Journal of International Law* p339

- I. The continuous and consistent use of the terms “ *national solidarity and independence*” throughout the Charter.
- II. Stronger emphasis on the Right to self-determination- although it can be found in the international treaties such as the UDHR and the ICCPR, the Afro-centric approach in the African Charter is clearly evident in Article 20 which bestows rights of *oppressed and colonized peoples’ to free themselves from the bonds of domination and colonialism.*
- III. A stark contrast with the Western approach can also be traced in Article 29 which places eight (8) very significant responsibilities on each individual *to work for the cohesion and respect of the family, to serve the country and to preserve national independence.*

Perhaps one would justify the placing of the duty to preserve national independence and to also serve the national country, as having been influenced by the liberation struggles and colonialism wars which most African countries fought in order to gain Independence. The argument by could be misleading

Additional examples can be traced in Articles 17, 18 , 23 and 14 of the Charter. These examples strongly demonstrate the extent to which the need for decolonization significantly and fundamentally shaped Africa’s approach to human rights. As **Viljoen (2011)** rightly asserts, African States have indeed to some extent adjusted human rights not only to better reflect their own understanding but to also address key issues of particular concern to Africa.⁵

However, interestingly, in approaching the human rights, African leaders did not pre-occupy themselves with the need to push for more economic and social rights such as the Right to rest and leisure⁶ , and the Right to science⁷. The justification could be that traditionally, in the yester years, in an African society, leisure, rest and science have not been viewed as integral components of a thriving society, but rather a luxury. Therefore African leaders, to some extent pushed back against the Eurocentric approach to human rights. Through this lens, it becomes clear that the argument various scholars to the effect that African people lacked their own conceptualization of human rights, could be very much misleading and ought to be approached with caution.

4. The Banjul Charter vis-à-vis the European Convention on Human Rights, and the American Convention on Human Rights.

On the other hand, another school of thought has correctly propounded that despite the Western influence on the concept of human rights, Africa’s personal and unique conceptions of human dignity and the balance between individual and community rights, inspired the

⁵ Viljoen “*Human Rights in Africa: Normative, institutional and functional complementarity and distinctiveness*” 2011, Vol 18, South Africa Journal of International Affairs p192

⁶ Art 24 UDHR

⁷ Art 25 UDHR

African Human Rights System⁸. It is without doubt that the Banjul Charter responds to African concerns, African traditions and African conditions. This view is better understood when one carefully studies the manner in which different regions have approached human rights, such as Europe and America on one hand, and Africa on another. Firstly, it is crucial to point out that a study of both the African Charter on Human and Peoples' rights and the European Convention on Human Rights demonstrates traceable consensus on the universality of Human rights. Both instruments in their Preambles, make reference to the UN Charter and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, as the foundations from which the instruments have drawn inspiration. Key universal approaches are noted in provisions on the Right to Life, Freedom from Torture, Right to personal liberty and security, Freedom from discrimination and the right to a family.

However, there also exists traceable nuanced differing approaches. For example, the Afrocentric approach can be traced on particularly on the continuous reference to "Peoples' rights". It is correct to argue that while the euro-centric approach appears to be predominately concerned with the protection of individual rights, the afro-centric approach is also concerned with collective rights, the rights of "Peoples". The naming of the Charter itself is quite telling on how Africa places importance on collectivism and solidarity. In studying the Banjul Charter, it is crucial to pay extra attention to the couching of certain rights, as below:

- I. Art 20 Peoples' right to existence, self-determination and to fight colonialism,
- II. Art 21-Peoples' right to dispose of their wealth,
- III. Art 22-Peoples' right to development,
- IV. Art 23-Peoples' right to national and international peace and security

On the other hand, with the European Convention on Human Rights continuously makes reference to "Everyone". Similarities can also be drawn with the American Human Rights Convention which The approach by the 2 regions does not differentiate between 'individuals and peoples'. A fundamental question then arises:- "Why does the Charter make reference to 'peoples?'. It therefore strengthens the view that the approach by African States was largely influenced by the need to identify and protect different ethnic groups as characterized throughout the continent. Chemhuru opines that the integration of certain African concepts into the African Human rights system "was more of a re-affirmation of already existing and valid African Human Rights imaginaries".⁹

5. The Protocol to the African Charter on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol), the SADC Protocol on Gender and Development *vis-à-vis* the Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination of Women (CEDAW).

⁸ M Chenhuru "African Communitarianism and Human Rights:-Towards a compatibilist view" 2018, Vol 65 Theoria-A journal of social and political theory p37.

⁹ M Chenhuru n8

The comparative analysis of the sectoral approach to human rights at different levels also illuminates the Afrocentric approach to human rights. The CEDAW was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly under Resolution 34/180 of 18 December 1979. Entering into force on 3 September 1981, the CEDAW up to this day remains the first ever international Treaty seeking to advance the rights of women through ending all forms of discrimination against women¹⁰. At regional level, pursuing the same goal of ending all forms of discrimination against women, the AU through the Assembly of the Union in 2003 adopted the Protocol To The African Charter On Human And Peoples' Rights On The Rights Of Women In Africa (Maputo Protocol). While both instruments pursue the same goal, a comparative analysis of the two demonstrates the extent to which Africa adopted a peculiar approach to create and recognise special rights of women. Through this unique approach, the African community placed greater importance on the need to emancipate African women from the shackles of historical and traditional biases manifest in the African community. Evidence of this can be traced in the following provisions of the Maputo Protocol:

- I. Art 5- Prohibition of harmful practices which adversely impacts the human rights of women, such as female genital mutilation.
- II. Art 14- The right to be protected from STIs including HIV and AIDs.
- III. Art 20- The right of widows to remarry.
- IV. Art 21- The right of women to inheritance.

This evidence supports the argument by RMD'Sa¹¹ that African cosmologies shaped the human rights discourse in Africa by addressing issues that are prevalent among ordinary Africans. This sui generis approach cannot be traced in both the European and American human rights systems. For example, while both the Charter of the Organization of American States¹² and the American Convention on Human Rights¹³ both provide for non-discrimination of all sexes, they do not expansively and comprehensively breakdown nuances of discrimination of women as demonstrated under the African approach. The European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms prohibits discrimination on any grounds, including sex, in the enjoyment of rights contained in the Convention¹⁴. In 2011, Europe adopted a new Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence, which however speaks specifically to addressing violence against women as it manifests with the Europe region. Neither the Inter-American system nor the Europe system speaks to issues of widows remarrying or the scourge of the HIV and AIDS, understandably because these issues have not been widely felt in the civilised two regions, as opposed to the African region. In other words, while these are foreign concepts to the West, it is a fundamental issue regarding as human right.

Scholars such as G Bekker, have strongly advanced the argument that in establishing an African Human rights system, African states were not concerned with protection of individual rights

¹⁰ <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/cedaw.pdf>

¹¹ RM D'Sa "Human Peoples' Rights-Distinctive Features of the African Charter" 1985, Vol 29 Journal of African Law p72

¹² Chapter II, Article 3 (l),

¹³ Art 1

¹⁴ Art 14

but more with consolidating their power through the principle of sovereignty. It may however, be challenging to accept this view today, particularly noting the further development and evolution of Africa's human rights system, especially when one interrogates the sectoral approach to human rights, particularly in regards to the protection of rights of vulnerable groups such as women and children at both the African region level and the international level.

6. The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child vis-à-vis the Convention on the Rights of the Child.

It is without doubt that pertaining to the rights of a child, both approaches by the United Nations, the European human rights system, the Inter-American Human rights system and African Union place emphasis on fundamental principles of the **best interest of the child**, non-discrimination, the right to survival and development. However, it is crucial to note that the African Charter, in its Afrocentric philosophy goes an extra-mile to recognise a set of rights which is not necessarily captured by the Convention. The Charter expressly incorporates the following rights:

- I. Art 21- Protection of the child from harmful social and cultural practices
- II. Art 26-Protection of the child from apartheid and discrimination.

Again here the justification here could be the same as the sectoral approach to the rights of women and the Maputo Protocol.

Furthermore, interesting to note is that by the definition of both the African Charter and the Convention, a child is a human being under the age of 18. Interestingly, with this definition in mind, the African Charter goes further to place a total of six spectacular and worrying obligations on the child. These are provided in Article 31 of the Charter. The strongly worded obligations include “ *to respect his superiors and elders, to preserve national solidarity and to strengthen the independence of the country.* ” Worrying as it may be, from an understanding of the African cosmology and tradition, it is not at surprising to find such provisions. It is a magnificent display of the African traditional values in their raw state. However, while it is a settled principle that rights are to be balanced with obligations, this Afrocentric approach on balancing rights and obligations of a child presents a stark contrast. It is neither conceivable nor legally feasible to expect f a child, at whatever age to strengthen the independence of his or her own country.” Admittedly, this provision has caused challenges within the children's rights sphere, which as a result in 2017, compelled the **African Committee of Experts on the Rights and Welfare of a Child** to issue a General comment¹⁵, in a very futile attempt to address the challenges and questions raised by Article 31 in understanding the extent to which children may exercise their responsibilities while at the same time enjoying their rights.

¹⁵ <https://africanlii.org/akn/aa-au/doc/general-comment/acerwc/2017/general-comment-on-article-31-acerwc/eng@2017-10-01>

This approach it can be said is heavily influenced by the historic practice where children as young as 15 would take arms to participate in liberation war struggles across the continent, thus demonstrating once again the influence of African cosmologies on human rights.

7. Conclusion

While human rights are generally accepted as universal and indivisible as provided by the Universal Declaration of Human rights, it ought to be emphasized that different regions and States have approached this concept of human rights with exceptions. For Africa, although its Human Rights system was largely borne out of the foundation of the UDHR, the ICCPR and the ICESCR, the African values played a critical role in revolutionising human rights within the African region. When faced with the mounting pressure Africa to adopt a Western human rights protection concept, Africa did not shy away from its own inherent struggles and concerns to address problematic issues such as colonialism, right to self-determination and protection of women from harmful traditional practices.